

**Environmental Crisis and Gotham City: An Eco-Marxist Reading of
*The Dark Knight Rises***

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Abstract

According to Karl Marx, "Labour is the father of material wealth, the earth is its mother" *Das Capital* (1976); to Bruce Wayne, the protagonist of the film, Gotham city is his father, mother as well as his beloved. On the other hand, will of the League of Shadow is to destroy the city of Gotham for its corrupted model. This paper is engaged to discuss environmental crisis in the film *The Dark Knight Rises* (2012) at the clash between capitalists' face Bruce Wayne (Batman in disguise) and pseudo-socialists faces Bane and Talia who are successors of the League of Shadow. It also engages in the discourse of anthropogenic activities of the capitalist force and in turn, pseudo-socialists, who instead of fighting against it, are aggravating that process in order to complete annihilation of the city. Each ideological side is at the will to fulfil their subjective agenda. Here, we have witnessed the extensive utilising of technology on behalf of the capitalists' force to win over the pseudo-socialists. Very surprisingly, instead of opposing the anthropogenic activities, Bane and his team themselves are utilising technological machineries to ensure complete annihilation of Gotham city. So, this paper is not only engaging to show the degradation of the environment or the Green by the capitalists but also, how it has been aggravated by the activities of the pseudo-socialists, through the lens of Eco-marxism.

Keywords: Capitalism, Eco-Marxism, False Narrative, Gotham City, Proletariat, Pseudo-socialists

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Artificial environment is created by capitalist force in the city of Gotham in *The Dark Knight Rises* (2012), and the so-called socialist force tries to destroy that artificially constructed environment. But unfortunately, it is being viewed from an alternative perspective. Here, battle is being fought between two opposite forces in terms of their ideology. If one is fighting against corruptions and becomes a good force among the citizens of Gotham, another is claimed to have fought against the false narrative of the oppressors who hold the power to subjugate the people of Gotham. But Christopher Nolan, the director of the film, tries to deconstruct the fine line which practically separates capitalists and socialists in terms of preserving environment. There are innumerable scenes in the film which depict the exploitations of environment. Environment itself is big issue in in terms of the Dark Knight Trilogy, which would be looked at from the core of this paper. The green has been used by the above mentioned two ideologically separate parties in a quite different way. Destructive force of communism can never be the preserver of society, rather acts as an agent of destroying harmony of society, which implies nothing but the monopolistic view of the director. The filmmaker has been failed in terms of holding his own unbiased opinion. The concept of 'Governmentality' is highly recommendable, especially, while dealing with false narrative about Harvey Dent, district attorney of Gotham City. That was occurred in *The Dark Knight* (2008), upon that fales narrative of its previous part of the film, the entire action of *The Dark Knight Rises* is based on. Later an act of law was introduced, having Harvey Dent as an idol in front and thousands of criminals are detent in the Blackgate jail. Nobody knew that fales narrative constructed was constructed by Bruce Wayne and Jim Gordon, commissioner of police. Besides, Bruce's training under Ra's Al Ghul and its settings, Bane's jail, Bruce dungeon and on the other hand underground experimental chamber of Lucius Fox are depicted as a binary model of presentations: one is associated with natural settings and another is about artificial space made for scientific activities. It is thought provoking and direct us to rethink about the entire film from Eco-marxists perspective. It is a term which was coined by German chemist Justus Von Liebig. It

is also called 'Red Green.' It addresses the issues of environmental degradation by anthropogenic activities. Here, by utilising technological power, industrialists get more profits, and according to this ideology, there is a relationship between man and nature. The central focus will be to know, how deep do we have a detrimental form of nature here in the film?

Those who are Eco-marxists blame the capitalist system to be the sole cause of environmental degradation. First, it was imperialism which had a tremendous effect on the lives of the natives, their property; and now globalization is a refined version of that oppression of the capitalists, but little bit in a roundabout way. Whether it is imperialism or globalization, there are almost same powers working behind it and that is none other than Western ideology. Now, with the inventions of various technologies, it added another level for those capitolly intensive industrialists. There is always an extensive utilisation of technologies within the film of Christopher Nolan, and *The Dark Knight Rises* (2012) is nothing except to that. In African countries tremendously deforestation is being taken place in order to build up various constructions to make that place compatible with their capitalist agenda. Eco-socialists want to overthrow capitalism by designing a harmonious human society, where it can the process of environmental sustainability be maintained. It advocates dismissing the capitalism and emphasizes on common ownership. It has been proven from the speech of Bane, the antagonist of the film or foil to Batman (Bruce Wayne):

" We take Gotham from the corrupt! The rich! The oppressors of generations who have kept you down with myths of opportunity, and we give it back to you... the people. Gotham is yours..." (*The Dark Knight Rises* 01:39)

Although, the real intention of Bane was only to destroy the city and nothing else. As two opposite forces are fighting in the film, surprisingly both of them claimed to have fought for the people of Gotham. But as unbiased audiences, we need to concentrate on true facts and its implications. This paper will mainly focus on its ecological issues and make a distinguished discourse through the lens of Eco-marxists perspective. Here, two parties claim to be serving in favour of environmental sustainability, and it becomes a complex scenario for researchers to come to any homogeneous point.

The reviews are in large number as this is a part of Dark Knight Trilogy, one of the world celebrated filmic presentations. Marxist approach has already been explored through the hands of various reviewers and writers. Political turmoil and revolutionary activities become the reality

after following numerous scenes related to corruptions. It is being negatively portrayed the presence of proletariats in Gotham city. Slavoj Zizek in "Dictatorship of the Proletariat in Gotham City" shows how does the ideological predicament impact Gotham society. Bane, a terrorist leader and member of the League of Shadow unveils the truth behind Dent Act and releases the prisoners from the Blackgate jail. He was in favour of overthrowing societal elites and restore power to the proletariats. The sacrifice of Batman will be remembered and while it has been shown that Bruce Wayne is died during riot. This means, people again are unknown about the reality, this how false narrative always prevails in society in a never-ending process. According to Zizek what Jim Gordon reads out at the funeral of Bruce Wayne (Batman in disguise), is taken from Charles Dickens' *A Tale of Two Cities* (1859):

"I see a beautiful city and a brilliant people rising from this abyss.
I see the lives for which I lay down my life, peaceful, useful, prosperous
and happy. I see that I hold a sanctuary in their hearts, and in the hearts
of their descendants, generations hence. It is a far, far better thing that
I do, than I have ever done; it is a far, far better rest that I go to, than
I have ever known." (*The Dark Knight Rises* 02:31- 02:32)

There were only Jim Gordon, Lucius Fox, John Blake, and Alfred Pennyworth at the funeral of Bruce Wayne. It's something similar with the tragic hero Jude in *Jude the Obscure* (1895), where Jude after spending a struggling life dies and not even gets proper funeral, with only attended his heartless wife Arabella and old widow Mrs Edlin. This paper also brings it in the forefront that that it "...rises to the noblest level of western art... An ultimate Christ figure, Batman sacrifices himself to save the others." As Jesus Christ dies to save people from their sins. Similarly, Batman sacrifices his life to save the corrupted men of the City of Gotham. This sort of elevation of Batman like figure closely resembles obsession with Western cultures. Nolan declined to have any left/right political implications in this film. Christopher Nolan is known as 'good liberal'. It acknowledges the economical disparity among the citizens of Gotham which ultimately results in revolution. Mr. Zizek pointed out about the business of Wayne Foundation and their dealings with arms and speculation on stock exchange market. That's the reason Bane first targeted stock market. Dickensian over moralisation and economical disparity in the shape of 'dishonesty', in the context of Gotham city. The violent form of communism has been criticized. It causes out of their failure on societal strategy, they simply indulge in violence. It has praised of the citizens resistance with true Gandhian nonviolent ideology. This also tries to present the League of Shadow along with Bane and his followers against the Western cultures, that is verified from the speech that

Bane delivered in front of Blackgate jail. Some Islamic forces might be Working as an inspiration to these extremists. We haven't been witnessed anyone indicating towards preserving the Green rather they tried to attack on nearly every establishment by the extremist group.

Jeff Ewing, an American film critic, wrote in "Two Complicated Economic Implications of the 'Dark Knight' Trilogy"; how Bruce Wayne has its pedigree in terms of civilising mission for Gotham City. It tries to link the narration with its earlier parts to its later part. Once Gotham got the train as the transportation system for the entire city; in *The Dark Knight Rises* (2012). Bruce Wayne's Company developed a fusion reactor to provide free and clean energy for the entire city, but it had to stopped on knowing that it could be turned into a nuclear weapon. Consequently, it becomes Bruce's responsibility to save his city. And in reality, he does so near the end of the film and apparently, sacrificed his life like Christ. It shows how the first and the last part of Batman films revolved around public goodness and services. Mr. Ewing said: "(... accessible public benefits)... transformed into dangerous city destroying weapons" and also superbly called, "... it takes a billionaire-industrialist - privatised-superhero to stop them." The idea of relating this film to the disaster of 9/11 attack on World Trade Center by Al-Qaeda is nothing new as Mridul Bordoloi brought in his paper "Re-packaging Disaster Post 9/11 and Christopher Nolan's The Dark Knight Trilogy." Looking at the revolutionary activities of Bane, the villain in *The Dark Knight Rises* or leader of the League of Shadow is being compared with the extremist activities of the organisation like Al-Qaeda quite fascinating. Professor Bordoloi has recognised the trilogy as 'cultural products'. He says, "... Christopher Nolan's The Dark Knight trilogy as texts that represent different types of the anarchic world view" (Mordoloi 87). The sole focus of this article was to read "'anarchy-as-disaster' in the context of the trilogy." He has formulated three different anarchic constructions for this trilogy. Emancipation has been stipulated to the dialogic charge on the final part of the trilogy. Emancipation is all pervasive in *The Dark Knight Rises* (2012), it means not only freeing the City of Gotham from the capitalists anarchy, where Bruce Wayne is venturing for new life with Selina Kyle, leaving all his properties behind, even his own manor for the asylum of the at risk children and becomes a proletariat like figure, but also freeing the city from the extremist group like the League of Shadow, who indulges in violence; as professor Mridul Bordoloi pointed out very well:

"Bane's communist-type revolution seems to be waged not actually to redress the exploitation of the proletariat, but to generate a utopian illusion of social equality through the destruction of the capitalist state apparatus, and then destroying Gotham altogether" (Mordoloi 95).

Dr. Sahar Ghumkhor, a lecturer in Criminology at Melbourne University, points out a very interesting fact, on the veil and the threat of terror in her article "To Veil the Threat of Terror: Law and the Other's question in The Dark Knight Rises." She opens up her paper with initial dialogue of Bane:

"It doesn't matter who we are; what matters is the plan.
No one cares who I was until I put on the mask."
Bane- *The Dark Knight Rises*

"The girls were victims, but they were also threats.
Veils were, after all, masks."
___ Joan Wallach Scott

She configures how does hidden face behind the veil has accelerated the controversy and the existence of a muslim women and their rights. Bane's appearance was terrifying, for he loses parts of his face during a scuffle in the jail in order to save Talia Al Ghul (Miranda, whom he loves); he was thrown away from the League of Shadow; so he also faces injustices personally. The relationship between Bane and Miranda is paralleled with the relationship between Bruce Wayne and Selina Kyle. The usages of mask in their relationships are rather quite connotative, Nolan is well known for putting special meaning to each and every scene within the film.

Christian parallelism is of intrinsic value in *The Dark Knight Rises*, which captures the essence of selfless devotion to human beings, as it has been portrayed in the film. According to Old Testament and Quranic verse Noah's (Nuh) flood had once washed away the entire lives on earth, for mankind's sins and corruptions. Similarly, in "The Dark Knight Rises: Christianity, Capitalism and Psychopathology", it has been constructed that Ra's Al Ghul seeks complete annihilation of Gotham City for its oppressive and corrupted model for human treatment. The parallelism between Bruce Wayne and Jesus Christ has come to the forefront; as both of them sacrificed their lives for the sins of others. But it needs to understand that Bruce Wayne practically belongs to that social strata, he himself was the creator of the false narrative. Interesting fact is, his sacrifice remains under the veil of mystery; or in the words of John Blake:

" I just can't take it. I mean, nobody will ever know who it was who saved an entire city.

Jim Gordon: They know who it was; it was the Batman"

_(*The Dark Knight Rises* 02:33)

Jim Gordon meant that they need to keep their mouths shut, here; so, he forbids Blake to tell the truth about Batman to anyone.

The papers have been mentioned are concerned about Marxist approach apart from the Eco-marxists view. Capitalism and its oppressive false narrative remain in focus; they discussed about the struggle between capitalists and revolutionary extremists. The objective of this paper is to explore the environmental degradation, which is being unaddressed yet, degradation due to the clash between these two ideological groups and makes a discourse through Eco-marxist lens. In the present filmic spectacles, violation in not only happening in the contrast between capitalists and socialists, rather it is happening at environmental level as well. The morality which Batman has adopted is not to kill anyone in his fight against the League of Shadow, but contrastingly the League members indulge in killings, bloodshed and mayhem. Christopher Nolan very calculatively depicted the life of Bruce Wayne from his childhood, apart from bloodshed, violence or any kind of violence; he is being lulled by his capitalist parents; he got all sorts of comforts and well beingness in his life. His life was changed after witnessing his parents are being shot in front of his eyes. On the other hand, Talia Al Ghul and Bane struggle hard in their prison lives and did not get any sort of those comforts that Bruce got. Surely, the children with struggling background are more prone towards violence, as this was the agenda of the filmmaker. Their characters generally shaped through the touch of nature which he got in his well-designed palace, but the nature that Talia Al Ghul and Bane had seen, something shaped their minds to be extremist. They acquired the knowledge of the darkside of life. Their childhood experiences are not something equal which shaped what they are. They are the product of different environmental phenomena. While Bruce was learning how to overcome fear, Talia Al Ghul was gathering fear, which ultimately helps her to escape from the hell like jail. Sources of fear were something that exist in nature come to Talia Al Ghul, and Bruce Wayne was in different form of experience.

21st century is an age of advanced technology and with-it growing population across the world is the hard reality. These simultaneous growings have an adverse impact on earth and its atmosphere. These sorts of technologies have often been used by those who want to make profit out of it. Nowadays, degrading environment becomes a daily basis activity for those profit-seekers. So, there is a conflict between common people and those profit-seekers; this implication is variedly connotative in *The Dark Knight Rises* (2012). The unsustainable use of the environments is the

prime reason behind this common tragedy of human beings; for that, many species, plants are at the verge of extinction. Capitalists always try to change the definition of lives. In the film this discourse becomes so difficult when a capitalist like Bruce Wayne is sacrificing his life to save the people of the city and for generations afterwards by taking the nuclear bomb out of the city. On the other hand, revolutionary leader of the League of Shadow tries to destroy the city. Mr. Nolan intentionally made the narrative complex by bringing various perspectives. This article explores for more such complex structures into the narrative, and how it is being affected on environment, would be explored through the lens of Eco-marxism. Eco-marxism is a socio-political ideology, comes in contrast with capitalism and their monopolistic attitude towards nature and their utilising process of that nature. Eco-marxists support sustainable environmental policies, although nowadays, that outlook slightly changed at least by observing the activities of the country like China who are claimed to be a socialist and communist country. Surely, this article would not want to be engaged in that discussion. Ecology has always been a part for scientific discourse, that is why, Eco-marxism just fills the gap by becoming a social analysis of ecological problems. There is a scene when Bruce Wayne comes to a charity ball and watches Selina Kyle was dancing with an old man. Here, Miranda appears with wearing a small mask, her appearance with that mask is very connotative. As we know, she is originally Talia Al Ghul, the daughter of Ra's Al Ghul, who comes to Gotham in order to take revenge against Bruce. Ra's Al Ghul and his next generation were in one line to destroy the city, and oppositely, Bruce Wayne and his family had been trying to save the city. Talia Al Ghul was well aware that Batman is originally Bruce Wayne, her appearance with that small mask is expressing that she knows Mr. Wayne's camouflage. Appearing with that mask is actually a kind of threat to Bruce Wayne's existence.

Bruce Wayne and Miranda Tate were engaged in the discussion of the clean energy project. As audiences know, the nuclear reactor was formulated on behalf of the Wayne Foundation to provide free energy to all over the state. But on knowing that, it could be turned into a nuclear bomb and that may cause a massive destruction to the city, they closed the project. In a way, this event provides sufficient reason for Wayne's exile or secluded life in his manor. Now, Miranda Tate takes up the project and hinting at Bruce:

"You have to invest to restore balance to the world.

Take clean energy project." (*The Dark Knight Rises* 00: 33)

Now, here comes the issue of Eco-marxism; company violating the rules of nature creates nuclear reactor. But interestingly, or I would rather call it as Nolan's cunningful directional skill; a capitalist company is making a project without thinking about its profits, so hyperbolic indeed!

Miranda Tate and Bane of took that opportunity to destroy the city utilising that same nuclear reactor. It has been speculated that how a project was made in order to serve the people, but ironically that becomes a weapon to destroy the same people. Using and utilising science and technology, capitalists are writing the destructive fate of human beings.

The mask plays fabulously connotative roles, where one can go to further onset. Almost all the leading characters are using mask, but what is different, is the purpose behind using that mask. Masks are actually materialising the faces of human beings; human face is one of the beautiful creations among other natural creations. Characters are not only hiding their faces with masks; they are hiding their inner desires as well. When it was asked by the officer Blake to Bruce Wayne that, why does he wear mask, it is for the safety of those who care you, love you, he said in reply. Sometimes, masks were used impliedly, for instance, Talia Al Ghul appears as Miranda Tate; nobody even could guess her to be the real mastermind of Bane. Her physical intimation with Bruce Wayne acts as a mask of hiding her identity, she even left no clue, indeed. On the other hand, Selina Kyle plays double game; firstly, with Bruce and lastly, with Bane. So, mask is a symbol; it is not used in a single dimension but has multiple connotative layers of understanding. Concrete masks are playing abstract purposes of the characters. This materialisation of masks is also paralleled with the anthropogenic activities on the face of nature by utilising various technological machineries. Nolan tries to make the discourse complex with the image of Wayne Foundation absolutely carefree about their profits. In terms of Eco-marxists view, industrialists are always capitally intensive. The family of Bruce Wayne is shown in the the film devoted to the welfare of the people of Gotham. But contrastively, they used to give funds to the orphan house out of their profits. The theme of charity is all pervasive throughout the film, such as, Selina Kyle was also engaged in the process of charity: she used to loot the upper class in order to spare on poor; as the industrialists like Bruce Wayne and his predecessors do for the city.

False Narrative about Harvey Dent and an act was passed in his name; The narrative is actually worked as an oppressive weapon to the upper class, by which they subjugate the criminals. Preventing those people in jail to get bail, implies they are bound to be detent at the will of the upper class. The concept of Biopower is a perfect example in which Michel Foucault argues that government exercises the power over the population in every aspect of human life. Here, that false narrative is closely associated with Foucault's another concept, Governmentality, it developes our understanding about power in a new way. He directs us to rethink about the social control through some unquestionable disciplinary institutions like jail, school, hospital. These were also being mentioned by Bane in his speech in front of Blackgate jail, but we need to understand that, he was

no longer wished to see the people of the city happy, rather wants to destroy them. On the other hand, the necessity for false narrative was also justified in the words of Jim Gordon:

" There's a point, far out there when the structures fail you, and the rules aren't weapons anymore, they're... shackles letting the bad guy get ahead. One day... you may face such a moment of crisis. And in that moment, I hope you have a friend like I did, to plunge their hands into the filth so that you can keep yours clean!"

___(*The Dark Knight Rises* 01:38-01:39)

Very interestingly, the moment nuclear reactor turns in a bomb, Bane kills Dr. Pavel, a nuclear physicist, who was only capable to stop the bomb in the front of all: through it Bane wants to raise fear among the citizens; Now the city is unsafe at the hands of those extremists. The reactor was made by Wayne Foundation, but later that was took over by the League of Shadow. It means now the product will no longer be controlled by its originator, rather would be controlled by other. Now master is being alienated from its product. Buildings, towers, bridges are created from capitalist efforts and being destroyed the League of Shadow. These sorts of creations are end products out of anthropogenic activities. There was a scene in *Batman Begins* (2005), where Bruce accidentally sets fire on the temple and it is burnt down; the temple was situated on the slop of a snowy mountain. This act of firing, violating the natural beauty and its calmness. Although, Bruce saves the life of Ra's Al Ghul, his master. Later in the same film Ra's Al Ghul too burns down Bruce's beautiful manor, which Ra considered justice is balanced.

With the end of each part of the film, Batman appears. A compact amalgamation of revenge, terror, love, sacrifice has tremendously hit the hearts of the audiences. The presence of bat helps the filmmaker to relate the spectacles with natural or environmental perspectives. Bat is a part of nature, it is a natural symbol of evil and fear, and was a source of fear too for little Bruce at first. Now, that fear is thematised throughout the film. In a scene when Bruce was imprisoned in Bane's jail, a blind prisoner told him:

"How can you move faster than possible, fight longer than possible without the most powerful impulse of the spirit: the fear of death." (*The Dark Knight Rises* 01:54)

The fear ultimately acts as a life force to leap towards impossible end; fear is needed, this is how fear transforms little Bruce from innocent to experience, fear is an experimental tool for him. Nature becomes a source of terror; bat is that element of nature. Similar subjective experience

Bane had to go through in prison. Bat and batcave are symbol of primitivity, and probably, thought to be connected with evil spirits, here juxtaposed with that of advanced technological weapons. Bruce Wayne chooses his disguised attire to be in shape of bat; materialisation of natural elements with the anthropogenic arts adds another dimension in this ecological discourse. Similarly, mask of scarecrow has also been used in previous parts which signifies the materialisation in the narrative. Creating a base in the bat cave beneath Wayne's manor is inspired from his childhood experiences of fear. The cave is a place, created naturally, but Wayne secretly made that place for executing his activities; it discloses the discourse of intruding anthropogenic force in a calm natural setting.

The perfect scene related to anthropogenic activities is when Bruce Wayne enters into the cave with specially designed plane; it makes a clear visual contrast to the audiences. A dark dungeon with a flowing fountain and suddenly, appears there a plane with its heavy sound, signifying contrast. Satyajit Ray was a master of using such contrast on screen; in *Jalsaghar* (The Music Room) (1958), it was the sound of Mahim Ganguly's jeep in contrast with landlord Biswambhar Roy's elephant and its trumpet and contrastive in transportation means as well. In *The Dark Knight Rises*, Bruce Wayne tries to hold the influence over the city, as his pedigrees done so before by capitalistic means. But Bruce Wayne, the new generation of that same pedigree sets his influence through the help of skill and knowledge and wants to leave his capitalistic identity behind. For, he is being associated with Selina Kyle, a jewel thief and belongs to the lower strata of society. In *Jalsaghar*, landlord Biswambhar Roy is trying hard to survive his Zamindari in post independent India and becomes a failure in the face of modernity. But in *The Dark Knight Rises* (2012,) after introduction of revolutionary movement in Gotham City, Bruce Wayne chooses to become saviour of the City, instead of becoming a capitalist and becomes successful. This is how, the influences of the upper class and their false narrative go on generation after generations in a never-ending process. Here, Bruce's Predecessors become tradition and Bruce Wayne found a superior and modern means to a make a place in the hearts of the citizens of Gotham. Similarly, in *Pather Panchali* (Song of the Little Road) (1955), the appearance of train with black smoke against the foreground of white Kash flower, where, black signifies corruption and pollution and white signifies the pure and unpolluted touch of nature. Mr. Ray was concerned about the contrastive presentation of tradition with modernity. In *Pather Panchali* train symbolises technology-based modernity, corruption, and Kash flowers symbolise innocent, pure, and fresh beauty of nature. Christopher Nolan called *Pather Panchali* "One of the best films ever made." The presence of technological elements simultaneously with natural elements is a challenge towards nature. In The Dark Knight Trilogy or particularly, in *The Dark Knight Rises* scientific inventions

and all machineries are presented to make a capitalist guy as a hero. Lucius Fox's inventions help Bruce Wayne to reproduce himself as Batman. These instruments were combinedly used to make one hero in front of the country men. But Bruce Wayne had to renounce his veil life ultimately, as Benjamin Winterhalter said:

" ... the most important political message in *The Dark Knight Rises* is the idea that one can, finally, leave one's demons behind. Leaving Batman behind means abandoning the political beliefs that Batman embodied." (Winterhalter 1046)

He had to renounce materialisation at the end, for it is evident that Alfred Pennyworth sees him at the café in Florence with Selina Kyle. This sort of renunciation was also depicted at the end of *The Dark Knight* (2008), where Lucius Fox had to destroy his system, Alfred burns the last letter of Rachel and Batman goes in and lived a secluded life in his manor for eight years.

At the end, nuclear bomb was carried out of the city towards the ocean by Batman with the help of his aerial craft, The Bat. Once again, the ocean environment is polluted. Batman becomes an idol to the citizens of Gotham; but what is devastating, he is becoming hero with compromising nature, by degrading it. Ultimately, the entire city remains unknown to his sacrifice; this is how, one too can become a hero! Wayne's entire life was filled with subjective emotions: the loss of his parents and Rachel Dawes, his beloved too; Bruce mourns over and said:

" Rachel died believing that we would be together; that was my life beyond the cape. I can't just move on. She didn't, she couldn't."
_ (The Dark Knight Rises 00:57)

These emotions remain constant throughout his life, and acts as a life force. The concern for environment has not been witnessed except to save the lives of the citizens at the end. It would be wrong to identify the League of Shadow as a group, inspired by Marxism, rather they are following a perspective, which they supposed to be an ideal one; we should not mix up the Marxist approach with that of monopolistic attitude. They are engaging in the task of killings, whoever disobey or challenge them. And the the League of Shadow is claimed to have provided true justice, and they are fighting against corruptions. They are typically pseudo-socialists, who in name giving justice only trying to fulfill their monopolistic agenda. The activities of the League of Shadow have been compared with Islamic extremist group like Al-Qaeda Bane and Talia Al Ghul came to Gotham not to provide justice to the people of the city, but to take revenge. They are intensified to

be died with the city or in reverse, it could be considered as a suicidal attempt, something similar with ISIS or other groups like Al-Qaeda. As exactly was done in 9/11 attack on World Trade Centre, in which Mohammad Atta and his fellows were died during the attack as here Bane and Talia Al Ghul died. It is true through World Trade Centre America tries to get a strong hold on global economy. They are on a mission to infiltrate globalization which is shameful, but the attack on the Centre is also condemnable. Similarly, Bruce Wayne and his family became a capitalistic hub and constructor of the false narrative of the city, which is wrong, and on the other hand turning a fusion reactor into a nuclear bomb is too a peerless crime which puts the lives of the millions in danger. Bane and his team were also not taking steps to save the environment. This is where Christopher Nolan tries to balance his liberal standpoint and lefts for the audiences to judge it.

Bane and his fellows were engaged to destroy the city and its almost every establishment; that too with the weapon, made by the citizens of Gotham. At the scene, when Bane was disclosing the truth behind the Dent Act and read out the letter of Jim Gordon standing on Batman's tumbler before Blackgate jail. This standing on tumbler is not only something helps him to creep up higher position to deliver his speech, yet, too, it has an implied meaning to look down upon the technical innovations. They have destroyed the sport ground to create the city, a valley of the deads. Near the end of the film Blake is getting ready to explore the bat cave of Bruce Wayne, before entering the cave, Blake is standing before a fountain, a beautiful scenario, which signifies contrastive phenomenal entity of complex, corrupted and experienced human mind is going to touch and affect beautiful nature through anthropogenic activities.

Though, Christopher Nolan gives efforts to bring light on both ideological sides in terms of their objectives for preserving sustainable environment; it is a concrete reality of the capitalistic exploitations of the Green. No one has taken any positive steps to preserve it. Muzomulhe Ntuli quotes Karl Marx from *Das Capital* (1976)_ "Labour is the father of material wealth, the earth is its mother." According to Marx, nature is equivalent entity of mother figure; surely, it might as well be observed from the activities of capitalists like Bruce Wayne and so-called socialist like Bane. From the side of Wayne, it is his motherland; his utmost desire to save it, he only concerns about its people, which is quite justified from the point of view of capitalists and never cared about its environment. On the other hand, there is completely a hypocritical ideal being carried off the League of Shadow with them. Ultimately, their justice remains the justice for their own will. Their revengeful soul can never spare time on the environment sustainability; their utmost desire is to destroy the city for its oppression, corruption, but they never cared about its nature, rather they are against the nature. In order to take revenge against certain people, they are planning to destroy the entire city, which is illogical. They are the outsiders and don't have any emotional connection

with the city; to Bruce Wayne this city is both, father and mother. This City has given him nothing except pain as Alfred said: "...I never wanted you to come back to Gotham. I always knew there was nothing here for you, except pain and tragedy" (*The Dark Knight Rises* 00:17). And he is giving his 'labour' to save it. While Bruce Wayne said in jail: "I do fear death. I fear dying in here, while my city burns, and there's no one there to save it" (*The Dark Knight Rises* 01:54). He can not remain inactive while his mother land is in danger. In spite of the fact, this city has snatched away his parents, his beloved, but he never leaves the city alone. His love for the city is like a soldier. Again, it does not empower anyone to exploit its environment. To present the pseudo-socialists against capitalists is not justified on behalf of the director. It is interesting to see a capitalist is becoming a proletariat to fight against those pseudo-socialists; he had to go through all sort of experiences that Bane and Talia had already gone through, who are supposed to be proletariat representatives under the veil to cater justice.

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